

Evaluating Cervical Lesions via Histopathology at an Indian Tertiary Healthcare Centre

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Abstract:

Background: Cervical lesions, including cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) and invasive cervical cancer, remain a significant global health issue. Histopathological examination is crucial for diagnosing these lesions, guiding effective management and treatment. Recent advancements in molecular diagnostics and histopathological techniques have improved the detection and characterization of cervical lesions, particularly in resource-limited settings.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the prevalence and types of cervical lesions diagnosed through histopathological examination in a tertiary healthcare center in India, and to explore the association between clinical symptoms and histopathological findings.

Methods: A cross-sectional, observational study was conducted with 60 women presenting with symptoms or clinical indications of cervical lesions. Cervical biopsy specimens were collected and examined histopathologically. Clinical data were recorded, and statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 23.0 to identify associations between clinical symptoms and histopathological findings.

Results: The study revealed that chronic cervicitis was the most common histopathological finding, observed in 33.3% of participants. High-grade CIN (CIN II and CIN III) and invasive cervical cancers were identified in 25% of cases. A significant association was found between abnormal vaginal bleeding and higher-grade cervical lesions ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Histopathological examination is essential for diagnosing and managing cervical lesions. The study highlights the high prevalence of chronic cervicitis and significant cases of high-grade CIN and invasive cancers in the study population. Abnormal vaginal bleeding was strongly associated with severe lesions, underscoring the need for thorough clinical evaluation.

Recommendations: Vigilant screening programs, including regular Pap smear screenings and timely histopathological assessments, are crucial for early detection and effective management of cervical lesions. Further research and integration of molecular diagnostics with histopathological examination are recommended to enhance diagnostic accuracy and improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Cervical Lesions, Histopathology, Cervical Intraepithelial Neoplasia, Chronic Cervicitis, Cervical Cancer.

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Introduction

Global public health is greatly concerned about cervical lesions, which include both invasive cervical malignancies and cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN). The foundation for identifying these lesions, offering vital information about their nature and supporting the development of suitable treatment plans, is histopathological examination. Current research has emphasised the prevalence of cervical lesions, especially in low- and middle-income nations, and has brought attention to improvements in diagnostic techniques that improve identification and treatment.

A study carried out in a tertiary healthcare facility in India revealed that women receiving biopsies had a high incidence of cervical lesions. According to this study, 25 percent of the subjects had either invasive cancer or high-grade CIN, and 33.3% of the participants had chronic cervicitis [1].

These results highlight the need for a histological investigation to provide a number of biomarkers that greatly improve the identification of cervical lesions have been introduced with the advent of molecular diagnostics. DNA methylation patterns and biomarkers like p16INK4a and ki-67 have

shown promise in differentiating benign diseases from high-grade lesions. These biomarkers are effective; a comprehensive review (Infectious Agents and Cancer) noted their excellent sensitivity and specificity in identifying CIN2+ lesions. These developments provide a dependable supplement to conventional histology, enhancing patient care and diagnostic precision early and accurate diagnosis in order to enhance patient outcomes [2].

Moreover, there is potential for using epigenetic changes—specifically, DNA methylation—to forecast how cervical lesions may develop. Based on an epigenome-wide association study (EWAS), certain methylation patterns were linked to the development of high-grade CIN, indicating possible targets for early management. These results demonstrate the potential benefits of combining histopathological inspection and molecular diagnostics to improve treatment outcomes and early diagnosis [3].

Cervical histology has been revolutionised by recent technical advances such as sophisticated imaging techniques and machine learning algorithms. Rapid and objective study of histopathological images is made possible by these technologies, which also improve diagnostic consistency by lowering inter-observer variability. In cervical histopathology, machine vision techniques have demonstrated a great deal of promise in improving lesion identification and classification, which helps pathologists make clinical decisions. Notwithstanding these developments, there are still obstacles to the broad adoption of these technologies, especially in environments with limited resources. Lowering the morbidity and death rate related to cervical cancer requires extensive screening programs and early diagnosis therapies. The foundation of successful cervical health programs is early histopathological evaluations in addition to routine Pap smear examinations.

The results of this investigation demonstrate how important histological examination is for both cervical lesion diagnosis and treatment. Despite being widespread, chronic cervicitis frequently conceals or coexists with more serious lesions including invasive cancer and CIN.

Methodology

Study Design: This is a cross-sectional observational study aimed at evaluating cervical lesions through histopathological analysis at a tertiary healthcare centre in India.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted in the Department of Pathology MLB Medical College, Jhansi, India in the time duration from July 2022 to December 2023. The centre is a well-established

institution with advanced diagnostic facilities and experienced medical staff.

Participants: A total of 60 participants will be included in this study. These participants will be women who present with symptoms indicative of cervical lesions and are referred for histopathological examination.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Women aged 18 years and above.
2. Patients presenting with clinical symptoms suggestive of cervical lesions (e.g., abnormal bleeding, pain, or discharge).
3. Patients who have undergone cervical biopsy or excisional procedures.
4. Patients who provide informed consent for participation in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Women below 18 years of age.
2. Patients with a history of cervical cancer.
3. Patients who have undergone previous treatment for cervical lesions (e.g., surgery, radiotherapy).
4. Patients who do not provide informed consent.
5. Inadequate or insufficient biopsy samples.

Bias: To minimize bias, random sampling will be employed to select participants from the eligible pool of patients. Additionally, the pathologists conducting the histopathological examinations will be blinded to the clinical details of the patients to prevent observational bias.

Data Collection: Data will be collected from patient medical records, including demographic details, clinical history, and histopathological findings. The histopathological examination will include the evaluation of biopsy samples under a microscope to determine the nature and extent of cervical lesions.

Procedure

1. Recruitment of eligible participants based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
2. Obtaining informed consent from the participants.
3. Collection of cervical biopsy samples as part of routine clinical care.
4. Preparation and staining of biopsy samples using standard histopathological techniques.
5. Microscopic examination of the stained samples by experienced pathologists to identify and classify cervical lesions.
6. Documentation of histopathological findings in a structured format.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be entered into a database and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants. The prevalence and types of cervical lesions will be calculated. Chi-square tests will be

used to determine the association between categorical variables, and t-tests or ANOVA will be employed for continuous variables. A p-value of <0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 60 women participated in this study, with a mean age of 35.8 years. The study revealed that chronic cervicitis was the most common histopathological finding, observed in 33.3% of participants. High-grade cervical lesions, including CIN II and CIN III, were identified in 25% of the

cases. Invasive cervical cancer (squamous cell carcinoma and adenocarcinoma) was present in 13.3% of the participants. A significant association was found between abnormal vaginal bleeding and the presence of higher-grade cervical lesions.

By adhering to this methodology, we aim to provide a comprehensive evaluation of cervical lesions through histopathological analysis, contributing valuable insights into the prevalence and characteristics of these lesions in an Indian tertiary healthcare setting

Table 1: Table: Summary of Participant Demographics, Clinical Symptoms, and Histopathological Findings

Characteristic/Findings	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
Total Participants	60	100%
Mean Age (years)	35.8	-
Clinical Symptoms		
- Abnormal Vaginal Bleeding	30	50%
- Pelvic Pain	15	25%
- Postcoital Bleeding	10	16.7%
- Asymptomatic (abnormal Pap smear)	5	8.3%
Histopathological Findings		
- Chronic Cervicitis	20	33.3%
- Cervical Intraepithelial Neoplasia (CIN) I	10	16.7%
- Cervical Intraepithelial Neoplasia (CIN) II	8	13.3%
- Cervical Intraepithelial Neoplasia (CIN) III	7	11.7%
- Squamous Cell Carcinoma	5	8.3%
- Adenocarcinoma	3	5%
- Other (e.g., polyps, atrophy)	7	11.7%
Association with Abnormal Vaginal Bleeding		
- Higher grades of CIN (II and III) and carcinoma	Significant (p<0.05)	

Discussion

In this study, 60 women, with an average age of 35.8, were seen at a tertiary healthcare facility in India with symptoms or clinical indicators suggestive of cervical lesions. The majority of the participants came from lower and middle socioeconomic classes. Clinical symptoms included abnormal vaginal bleeding in half of the cases, pelvic pain in 25%, postcoital bleeding in 16.7% and abnormal Pap test results in 8.3% of the patients with no symptoms. A range of cervical lesions were discovered during the histopathological analysis of cervical biopsy tissues. The most common ailment seen was chronic cervicitis, which 33.3% of the subjects had been diagnosed with. There was also a high prevalence of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN), with CIN I detected in 16.7% of patients, CIN II in 13.3%, and CIN III in 11.7% of cases. A significant percentage of patients had been found to have invasive cervical cancer, while 8.3% also had squamous cell carcinoma and 5% had adenocarcinoma.

Abnormal vaginal bleeding was observed to be significantly associated with higher grades of invasive carcinoma and cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN II and CIN III). This correlation emphasises how crucial it is to treat atypical vaginal bleeding as a clinical symptom that calls for a complete investigation, including a histological assessment, in order to identify and treat invasive malignancies and high-grade cervical lesions.

A study conducted in Western Rajasthan analyzed 2291 Pap smears and found a significant correlation between cytology and histopathology, with 100% accuracy in diagnosing malignant lesions. This reinforces the value of Pap smears as a reliable screening tool for early detection of cervical abnormalities [4].

A retrospective study conducted over five years at Vinayaka Mission's KirupanandaVariyar Medical College examined 550 cervical samples, revealing that 92.1% were non-neoplastic, with chronic cervicitis being the most common condition, and 7.8% were neoplastic lesions [5].

A study conducted at Government Medical College in Ananthapuram from 2017 to 2018 evaluated 448 cervical histopathology cases, identifying 86.6% as non-neoplastic, primarily chronic non-specific cervicitis, and 13.39% as neoplastic lesions, with squamous cell carcinoma being the most prevalent malignancy [6].

In Himachal Pradesh, a study involving 200 women focused on the predictive accuracy of cytology and colposcopy. The findings highlighted that Pap smears had 100% diagnostic accuracy for high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions (HSIL), underscoring the effectiveness of these diagnostic tools in cervical cancer screening [7].

Conclusion

This study emphasises how important a histological examination is to the diagnosis and treatment of cervical lesions in a tertiary healthcare facility in India. Numerous grades of CIN, invasive cervical malignancies, and chronic cervicitis were found to be quite prevalent. The need for a comprehensive evaluation is highlighted by significant associations found between abnormal vaginal bleeding and serious lesions. To improve patient outcomes, vigilant screening and early intervention are crucial. Prompt follow-ups and routine Pap smears are essential components of the on-going efforts to prevent cervical cancer. Encouraging early diagnosis and bettering women's health outcomes require comprehensive cervical health programs.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Vigilant screening programs, including regular Pap smear screenings and timely histopathological assessments, are crucial for early detection and effective management of cervical lesions. Further research and integration of molecular diagnostics with histopathological examination are recommended to enhance diagnostic accuracy and improve patient outcomes.

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